

The top performer: Towards optimized parameters for reduced graphene oxide uniformity by spin coating

Ciril Reiner-Rozman^{1,2} | Roger Hasler¹ | Jakob Andersson¹ | Teresa Rodrigues¹ | Anil Bozdogan³ | Johannes Binting^{1,2} | Patrik Aspermaier¹

¹ Biosensor Technologies, Austrian Institute of Technology, Konrad-Lorenz Strasse 24, Tulln an der Donau 3420, Austria

² Danube Private University, Steiner Landstraße 124, 3500 Krems an der Donau

³ CEST Kompetenzzentrum für elektrochemische Oberflächentechnologie GmbH, Viktor Kaplan Straße 2, Wiener Neustadt 2700, Austria

Correspondence

Ciril Reiner-Rozman, Biosensor Technologies, Austrian Institute of Technology, Konrad-Lorenz Strasse 24, Tulln an der Donau 3420, Austria.
Email: Ciril.Reiner-Rozman@ait.ac.at

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Reduced graphene oxide has shown great potential for the fabrication of different electronic devices, especially biosensors and electric circuits. It allows the usage of simple deposition techniques such as drop casting or spin coating of graphene oxide solutions with a subsequent chemical, electrochemical, and/or thermal reduction to reduced graphene oxide. However, the utilized deposition strategy requires a defined protocol that ensures reproducibility. A study on a range of concentrations of GO and spin coating parameters is presented, aiming at the most uniform layers consisting of only single and double sheets for the application in electronic devices. The effect of film deposition on morphological parameters like the number of layers, overlaps, and surface coverage as well as the influence on electronic properties such as baseline stability and the transfer characteristics for the application as an electrolyte gated field-effect transistor (EG-FET) are shown. Best film characteristics and electronic properties are achieved by using a GO concentration of 214 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ applied via spin coating with 1800 rpm, after surface modification with adhesive layer.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Since its first isolation by mechanical exfoliation in 2004, graphene has increasingly captured attention as a novel nanomaterial [1]. It has become a crucial component in a variety of electronic applications [2] due to its unique properties. Several methods have been developed that can produce high-quality graphene, however ‘chemical vapour deposition (CVD)’ and reduction of graphene oxide are considered the most suitable to obtain graphene with high carrier mobility and low defect density. While graphene produced via CVD typically has large area uniformity with high electric and morphological reproducibility [3, 4], the production is very time and energy consuming and has low yields [5] compared to graphene obtained via reduction of graphene oxide. This method produces high yields but is generally perceived by the research community to produce graphene with less favourable properties for most applications and inferior homogeneity when compared to the pristine, CVD-grown material. ‘Reduced graphene oxide (rGO)’ is prepared via the reduction of graphene oxide by thermal, chemical

or electrical treatments. Even after reduction, it retains some oxygen functional groups (hydroxyl, epoxide, carbonyl and carboxyl groups) on the rGO surface. Different carbon to oxygen ratios and chemical compositions are obtained depending on the reducing agent. This can be exploited since rGO can be modified depending on the functional groups it contains, whereas CVD graphene cannot. Moreover, despite CVD resulting in self-limiting graphene formation on top of a metal surface with excellent step coverage [3], graphene deposition is followed by a transfer process to the desired substrate and removal of the metal by an etching agent which is a crucial step that is susceptible to human error. As such, despite the uniformity, the transfer process is a major disadvantage when using CVD-grown graphene. On the other hand, graphene oxide (GO) is directly deposited on the desired substrate and then reduced, which simplifies device production and eliminates a significant source of error. The use of reduced graphene oxide (rGO) simplifies device fabrication and can be used for bulk manufacturing but allows lower control over flake morphology and defect distribution as well as the chemical properties since the reduction

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cannot remove all structural defects introduced by the oxidation process. A further issue is the coagulation of rGO in solution, which leads to graphitic structures. As a result, the reproducibility during the fabrication of electronic devices will be compromised. In literature, GO is most commonly deposited on the substrate by drop casting, resulting in low reproducibility of surface morphology. On the other hand, spin-coating of GO offers a cost- and time-efficient alternative for the fabrication of uniform films; it is a less prominent but nevertheless established method for the fabrication of electronic devices [6, 7] including solar cells [8], electrodes [9], transistors [10], memory devices [11], membranes [12] and biosensors [13, 14]. Although this method has been widely used since the development of graphene films, only few publications investigate the outcomes of GO concentration and spin coating parameters on the electrical and morphological properties of the resulting devices. In this communication, we demonstrate significantly improved reproducibility of graphene film morphology and electrical properties using an optimized spin-coating deposition and handling strategy. We present a study on a range of concentrations of GO and spin coating parameters to produce uniform layers consisting of only single and double sheets for the application in electronic devices. We show the effect of film deposition on morphological parameters like number of layers, overlaps and surface coverage as well as the influence on electrical properties such as baseline stability and the transfer characteristics for the application as an 'electrolyte gated field-effect transistor (EG-FET)' based on rGO.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

ED-IDE1-Au (w/o SU8) with interdigitated electrodes (split with 10 μm , channel length 490 nm) were purchased by Micrux Technologies and used as substrates. The substrates were cleaned with a 1% Hellmanex II aqueous solution in an ultrasonication bath for 15 min, rinsed with Milli-Q grade DI-H₂O and sonicated for 15 min in DI-H₂O, rinsed with ethanol and sonicated for 15 min in ethanol. '(3-Aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES)' was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and used as adhesive layer for GO deposition. The clean substrates in ethanol were directly transferred and submerged for 1 h at room temperature in a 1% APTES solution, prepared in HPLC grade ethanol, covered for protection against UV-light. The substrates were then thoroughly rinsed with HPLC grade ethanol and dried with N₂ gas until complete dryness. The substrates were then heated to 120 °C for 1 h and left to cool down to room-temperature. Highly concentrated GO was purchased from Graphenea (0.4 wt%) and dilutions were prepared with Mill-Q grade DI-H₂O to obtain dilutions of 1:7, 1:14, 1:21, 1:28, 1:56 corresponding to 0.059, 0.029, 0.019, 0.014 and 0.007 wt% or 570, 285, 214, 143 and 72 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of GO in solution. Prior experiments were conducted to find this range of GO concentrations suitable for application via spin-coating. The GO stock solution was vortexed for 30 s using a VWR analogue vortex mixer at highest speed before preparation of the dilutions. To eliminate any

graphene conglomerates from the solution, resulting dilutions were transferred to Eppendorf vials (1 mL) and centrifuged for 20 s. For deposition on the substrates only the top portion of the resulting solutions was used for spin-coating. During the performed studies it was observed that correct positioning of the substrate on the spin-coater is critical to obtain optimal GO distribution. The devices were placed slightly off-centre, in such a manner that the rotational axis during spin coating is offset from the interdigitated area by 1 mm, omitting weakly covered spots at this axis. The prepared GO solutions were drop cast on the previously positioned substrates only a second before starting the spin-coater rotation. For the spin coating process, the steepest possible ramp (0 s) was chosen and the rotation speed of 900, 1200, 1500, 1800, 2100 was held constant for exactly 60 s. When finished, the coated substrates were immediately removed and submerged in Milli-Q grade DI-H₂O to stop any further adhesion from the solution. Each substrate was then washed with DI-H₂O and dried with nitrogen again. The described steps were performed consecutively without time gaps. The obtained GO-coated substrates were then reduced in reagent grade hydrazine monohydrate vapour (98%, Sigma-Aldrich) at 80 °C for 16 h. For this, the substrates were placed centred in glass petri-dishes and 1 mL of hydrazine was distributed concentrically around the edge of the dish, followed by immediate hermetical sealing of the petri-dishes and inserting them in the oven. After 16 h, the substrates were cooled to room temperature and the seal was opened, allowing any excess hydrazine vapour to evaporate for 1 h. The substrates were then heated to 200 °C for a thermal annealing step, after which the substrates were ready to use for characterization with a 'scanning electron microscope (SEM)' (Zeiss SUPRA 40 Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope) and consecutively for electrical characterization using a Keithley 4200-SCS probe station. For the electrolyte-gated configuration of the transistors a flow cell with 2 mm channel width and an Ag/AgCl gate electrode was used, enabling real-time flow measurements of the device baseline drift. Upmost attention was paid to the connection via BNC Triax cables, reducing any eventual noise not originating from the substrates, which in this state already were used as EG-FETs. To evaluate the device baseline drift, all sensors were rinsed with 1× PBS buffer solution in the flow-cell setup for exactly 10 min before their baseline was recorded with an applied source-drain voltage of 50 mV, applying a -400 mV potential at the gate electrode. After that the I_DV_G transfer characteristics were recorded. All experiments were performed with 300 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ PBS buffer flow speed.

3 | RESULTS

The devices were investigated with a SEM and the images were evaluated using ImageJ software to determine the rGO surface coverage on the substrates. This procedure is described in detail in the Supporting Information. Figure 1 shows the difference in spin coating rpm in the range from 1500 to 2100 for a GO solution with 214 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Surface coverages of these substrates increase with lower rotation speeds during spin coating. This is

FIGURE 1 SEM image comparison of three different spin coating speeds for a 214 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ GO solution. A) 2100 rpm B) 1800 rpm C) 1500 rpm. All images were recorded at 1000X magnification

FIGURE 2 Dependence of the fabricated device surface coverage on the spin coating rpm for different GO concentrations

a result of higher centrifugal forces during deposition and hence less surface contact and incubation time of the GO solution on the substrate. In detail, 2100 rpm resulted in 63% surface coverage, 1800 rpm in 76% and 1500 in 89%. In Figure 2, the surface coverages obtained for the selected ranges of dilution and spin coating parameters are shown. Interestingly, surface coverage depends linearly on GO concentration, while the relationship between spin coating speed and surface coverage density is also linear for a narrow RPM regime (as shown in Figure 2) but is more complicated for very high or low RPM number. Taking the standard error during device fabrication into account, the results shown in Figure 2 show a clear difference for speeds of 900 and 1200 rpm with higher coverages, while for higher rpm numbers from 1500 to 2100, surface coverage is similar. On the other hand, for the 8 devices fabricated with each of the parameters, the statistical evaluation shows the smallest standard error for 1800 rpm, (1.4%, shown in Figure 3) while 2100 and 1500 rpm devices varied by 2.5% and 2.3%, respectively. Hence, the decision was made to use 1800 rpm deposition speed with a GO concentration of 285 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for electrical characterization. It must be noted that a higher GO concentration (e.g. 570 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) with a higher rotation speed (e.g. 2500 rpm) might produce a similar result, but we did not evaluate these parameters. In general, we suspect that plotting the coverage versus the

FIGURE 3 Reproducibility of surface coverage for 8 fabricated devices for different GO concentrations with a spin coating speed of 1800 rpm

rpm and concentration as shown in Figure 2 for a wider range than shown here may well result in a linear ideal regime to obtain a morphology close to a monolayer where either the concentration and rpm are lowered or both parameters are increased, but in the work presented here, the relationship was not characterized to this extent.

As shown in Figure 3, the surface coverage reproducibility is better (standard error of 1.4%) for devices that have higher coverage due to the application of higher GO concentration (in this case 285 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) than for devices that have lower coverage due to a lower concentration of GO (214, 143 and 72 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) applied. This is expected if we take into consideration the extrapolated case of total surface coverage, with the whole surface being coated there is less variability in the production from device to device. On the other hand, Figure 3 gives no information about the quantity of multilayer structures, but as can be seen from Figure 1, the used concentrations and rotation speeds for spin coating were optimized beforehand to minimize the formation of multilayers and achieve surfaces with few overlaps of the rGO flakes to minimize the effects of intercalation of water molecules between those layers.

Interestingly, the GO distribution on the surface was found to vary depending if either a substrate with interdigitated electrodes or blank Si/SiO₂ substrates were used, although

in both cases the surface was modified with APTES and the fabrication was done using the same protocols. For the highest concentration of $570 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, the evaluation of multilayers was estimated via the SEM images and an estimated 50% or more of the device areas were found to be covered with at least 2 layers (Supporting Information). We expect that this originates from the uneven topology of the electrode surface with a few nm height profiles, where during the spin coating process the GO sheets stagger and form more overlaps in comparison to the deposition on blank substrates. Another aspect is the generally different smoothness of the used substrates, since the used Si/SiO₂ wafers are fabricated to produce ultra-low roughness while the commercially available devices with electrodes are manufactured with focus on the electrode precision and not on the substrate smoothness. Substrate roughness may also increase during the etching process required for electrode fabrication.

During the development of the protocols and tests for this study, we also examined the influence of graphitic structures on the topography and electronic performance. When applying GO via drop casting, the incubation time was always set to one hour, which is a significant amount of time during which graphene layers might agglomerate, forming graphitic structures. This could be avoided by varying the incubation time as well as the GO concentration used during drop casting. Still, for all variations of these parameters that were tested preceding this study, no suitable parameters were found to accurately control the surface coverage reproducibility and to avoid the formation of multilayered structures. In general, a major concern regarding graphitic structures is the instability of the attachment, since only relatively weak van der Waals forces hold multilayered structures together, resulting in significant variation in layer-to-layer distance. This also allows for the intercalation of molecules, especially ions, which can affect the electrical properties of the device as well as impurities, which are by definition a disadvantage of using rGO. Impurities have the most significant impact on sheet properties when located at the transition from one rGO flake to another, as they have the largest impact on percolation pathways in these locations. Furthermore, multilayers and graphitic structures may cause an ablation of a future surface functionalization or a signal attenuation of a binding event taking place on a recognition unit attached to such structures. Despite these disadvantages, the quick applicability and mass production capabilities of rGO are superior to perfectly uniform produced CVD graphene which does not suffer from multilayer formation and the associated deterioration in device properties.

Another advantage of rGO is the modified bandgap in comparison to CVD graphene. CVD graphene is a zero gap semi-metal, which makes the on-off ratio of graphene field effect transistors very low (<10) compared to conventional CMOS technologies, where ratios exceeding 10^7 are commonly achieved. As such, there have been some efforts to open the bandgap of graphene using different bandgap engineering techniques, such as using bilayer graphene or graphene nanoribbons [15]. Contrariwise, rGO resulting from most synthesis methods is a semiconducting material, exhibiting a significant gap

FIGURE 4 $I_D V_G$ reproducibility of eight FETs fabricated with 1800 rpm and $285 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ GO solution. The I_{DS} currents of the used chips were subtracted from their Dirac point (minimum) respectively for better visual comparison

from the valence to the conduction band with a lower density of states than CVD graphene. High variations resulting from different methods of production of rGO regarding the chemical properties and defects, e.g. carbonyl, epoxy or hydroxyl [16] as well as the oxidation state depending on the used reduction method [17] have been reported. The reduction method significantly influences the semiconducting properties of the resulting films. However, commercial sources of GO are available that offer high reproducibility in terms of chemical surface features. Regardless, the application of such GO solutions requires a defined protocol to optimize reproducibility.

For the electrical evaluation of the EG-FETs, the transfer characteristics were measured (Figure 4) and the baseline drift was evaluated after initial stabilization for a period of ten minutes (Figure 5).

The basic relationship describing the measured drain-source current for an EG-FET is given by the following equation:

$$I_{DS} = W/L C_i \mu [V_{GS} - V_T] V_{DS} \quad (1)$$

where I_{DS} is the drain-source current, W the channel width, L the channel length, C_i the capacitance of the system in respect to the ionic liquid, μ the charge carrier mobility in the semiconductor channel, V_{GS} the applied Gate voltage, V_T the threshold voltage and V_{DS} the applied voltage from source to drain. This basic equation does not explicitly consider any chemical reactions between the buffer solution and rGO. Instead, these effects are described implicitly by V_T and C_i since these parameters are obtained from the properties of the device with regard to its current state at observation. As can be seen in Equation (1), the capacitance and the mobility of the FET have a significant impact on the transconductance and I_{DS} current of the device and since these parameters are altered by the formation of multilayers and the topography in general, the application method has impact on the FET performance. Furthermore, it

FIGURE 5 A) Baseline drifts shown as the change in normalized I_{DS} as a percentage for FETs fabricated with different GO dilutions from 6.25 to 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with an applied V_{GS} of -0.4 V. B) The baseline drifts per minute obtained from (A) in correlation to the used GO solution concentration. C) Baseline drifts of spin coated rGO FETs shown as the change in normalized I_{DS} as a percentage (214 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of GO applied with 1200, 1800 and 2100 rpm)

has been shown previously that protonation and especially intercalation effects of the buffer solution in biological applications play a crucial role in the stability of an electrolyte gated FET device and its baseline drift [18–20].

A major prerequisite for the fabrication of surfaces was to reduce the number of graphitic structures, which, as argued above, is possible with the used spin coating method. Regardless, an initial centrifugation step was implemented before GO application to remove any graphitic structures from the solutions. Still, during this study it was observed that excessive centrifugation or ultrasonication (to exfoliate graphitic structures) resulted in smaller flake sizes. We optimized the centrifugation time to reduce the amount of graphitic structures while maintaining optimal flake size such that a single graphene flake could bridge the gap between electrodes. Graphite is a conducting material and in an interdigitated electrode configuration it presents a major challenge, since one such particle connecting

both electrodes will be significantly more conductive than the rGO sheets [21]. Electrically, this can be understood as a parallel circuit of resistors, where a graphitic structure can decrease the resistance of the FETs. Extrapolating from the SEM images of a surface deposited with 1800 rpm and 214 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, counting the connections from source to drain, approximately 10^5 parallel connections were found for the whole device fabricated with which the electrical characterization was performed for this study. This means that the total resistance of the FET will be lower than the resistance of the most conductive connection and the majority of current flow will be found at that connection. Hence, for most applications it is crucial to fabricate devices where the connection with lowest resistance is the material of interest, in this study being rGO and therefore it is crucial to reduce the number of graphitic structures, as we have done in this study by centrifugation and the choice of suitable spin-coating parameters.

The reproducibility of the fabricated FETs was experimentally verified by the measurements of the $I_D V_G$ response curves to obtain the transconductances of the p-type and n-type charge carriers. In our experience, these response curves are the significant go-to parameter to evaluate the suitability of the devices for a wide range of applications from biosensing, electronic circuits and more. To the best of our knowledge, no other studies have tackled the issue of $I_D V_G$ reproducibility for rGO-based FETs, but it is of utmost importance to make progress towards the fabrication of a commercially available device. Originating from biosensing, our team emphasizes the usability of the resulting EG-FETs for application such as biosensors, focusing on reproducibility, the ability to functionalize the rGO and the devices stability with regard to noise levels and baseline drift. For the evaluation of baseline drift as standard parameters, a 50 mV voltage from source to drain and a gate potential V_G of -400 mV were applied and a physiological PBS buffer solution with 150 mM concentration and pH 7.4 was used.

The results of this evaluation are shown in Figure 5(A) for drop casted rGO FETs and in Figure 5(B) for spin coated rGO FETs. Interestingly, the base line stability of devices fabricated by drop casted rGO depends on the rGO, shown in Figure 5(B). On the other hand, the base line stability of devices fabricated by spin coating does not depend on rotation speed. Furthermore, it appears that when reducing the amount of flake overlaps and multilayers, baseline drift is already in a minimal regime and the observed variations are merely a statistical feature. In detail, the drift for 1200 rpm is 0.04%/min, for 1500 rpm 0.08%/min and for 2100 rpm 0.07%/min. These results are similar to chips prepared *via* drop casting with 6.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (which seems to be around the minimum as seen in Figure 5(B)). However, the devices fabricated by drop casting with such a low GO concentration exhibited very low conductivity and reproducibility, having a wide range of different $I_D V_G$ response curves (Supporting Information). It has been proposed that layer overlaps which lead to intercalation effects could be responsible for the baseline stability of an EG-FET device [22]. By reducing the number of intercalation sites during the herein presented optimization via spin-coating, a reduction of baseline drift and stability was observed, further supporting this argument. As shown in Figure 5, the drifts for drop casted and spin coated rGO were compared under the same conditions and a clear difference was observed, showing significantly higher baseline stability for spin coated rGO FETs.

We therefore argue that by using spin coating with the described parameters we can significantly improve the reproducibility of chip resistance, surface coverage and transfer characteristics. Other methods failed to achieve reproducibility of all these crucial parameters simultaneously.

4 | CONCLUSION

We have described an optimized deposition protocol rGO on silica-based substrates. After investigation of the surface morphology and considerations of the effects of graphitic structures and intercalation, based on the surface coverage and electronic

properties a GO solution of 214 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ applied via spin coating with 1800 rpm was found to be most suitable for the fabrication of uniform films. Electrical reproducibility with regards to the transfer characteristics was demonstrated and found to be suitable for the fabrication of different devices, especially biosensors or electronic circuit switches which can also be fabricated on flexible substrates. The devices were tested for their stability regarding baseline drift and found to be significantly superior to drop casted FETs using the same materials. We conclude that spin coating is a significant improvement for the fabrication of well-defined electronic devices using rGO and intend to offer a guideline to members of the community to enable easier handling and fabrication GO- or rGO-based sensing devices.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of the article.

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